

(Table 2). Longer than 1 wk decomposition had no significant effect. Although high ESP significantly reduced biomass turnover and N contribution of sesbania, it had no effect on yield. ESP levels were substantially reduced after harvest. □

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Physiology and plant nutrition

Influence of new terpenoid analogue of abscisic acid on chilling resistance of rice seedlings

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We studied the effect of the new terpenoid analogue of abscisic acid of the acetylene-acetate type coded LAB 173711 (see figure) on resistance to chilling in 14-d-old rice seedlings.

Seedlings were sprayed with LAB 173711, at 10^{-3} mol/liter, maintained in a glasshouse at 29/ 21 °C day/night temperature, 12 h photoperiod, and 80% relative humidity for 24 h, then transferred to a chamber at 5 °C temperature for 3 and 5 d. Recovery in the glasshouse was monitored for several days.

Survival in unprotected plants chilled for 3 d was 60% 2 d after treatment (DAT); no plants survived 5 DAT (Table 1). Plants sprayed with LAB

173711 had 100% survival. The number of plants surviving 5 °C for 5 d was similar.

The analogue also protected the root system (Table 2). The number of

adventitious roots, root length, and root weight were higher in treated plants. The stability of the root system may contribute to the increased survival rate in protected plants. The increase in chilling tolerance may also be due to the direct action of analogue 173711 on stomatal closure; that prevented water loss through transpiration. □

Table 1. Survival of rice plants treated with LAB 173711, chilled at 5 °C for 3 and 5 d, and returned to 29 °C for recovery. Data are means ± SE of 3 parallel experiments with 10 plants each.

Treatment	Survival (%) with given time at 29 °C				
	1 d	2 d	4 d	6 d	8 d
<i>Chilled for 3 d</i>					
Control	100.0 ± 0	60.0 ± 5.8	23.33 ± 6.6	0	0
With 173711	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0
<i>Chilled for 5 d</i>					
Control	100.0 ± 0	44.0 ± 3.2	0	0	0
With 173711	100.0 ± 0	74.0 ± 6.6	68.0 ± 11.1	30.0 ± 4.1	30.0 ± 4.1

Table 2. Root growth of rice plants treated with LAB 173711, chilled at 5 °C for 2 d, and returned to 29 °C for 7 d recovery.^a

Treatment	Nodal roots ^a (no./plant)	Length ^b (cm)	Fresh weight ^b (mg)	Dry weight ^b (mg)
Control	17.0 ± 1.8	9.9 ± 1.2	205.8 ± 28.3	27.7 ± 7.0
173711	26.2 ± 1.7	14.7 ± 2.2	770.8 ± 28.0	69.2 ± 7.0

^a Data are means ± SE of 5 measurements. ^b Data are means ±SE of 8 measurements.

Chemical structures of abscisic acid (ABA) and of its terpenoid analogue LAB 173711.

Crop management

Effect of planting overage seedlings on rice duration, yield, and yield attributes

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Varietal differences in growth duration are due primarily to differences in length of the vegetative phase. We studied 15 prerelease cultures and varieties in the 1983 wet season. The field experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with three replications. Due to an unprecedented severe drought, 54-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 2-3 seedlings/hill spaced 15 × 15 cm.

The maturity of short-duration varieties (95-120 d) was prolonged to

108-134 d, primarily because of delayed flowering (see table). The maturity of medium-duration varieties (125 to 140 d) was not extended.

Extended duration differed among varieties. The differences in maturity in short-duration varieties could not be associated with their expected duration. Duration of 113-d Cul. 1954 was extended by 9 d, that of 108-d Cul. 25337 by 26 d. The capacity to extend the growth period, and thereby the duration, could be a varietal character independent of actual duration.

Grain yield was independent of duration. Cul. 4, MO.5, Karthika, and Jyothi had high yields; Cul. 126, Cul. 43-1-4, Cul. 25331, Bhagya, and Onam, low yields. Panicles/hill and 1,000-grain weight showed a similar trend. The drought stress experienced in the nursery might have persisted after transplanting in some varieties, while other varieties recovered during subsequent growth. Varieties capable of adjusting duration could be recommended for conditions when a delay in transplanting can be anticipated. □

Days to 50% flowering, duration, panicles/hill, 1000-grain weight, and grain yield of cultures and varieties. Kerala, India, 1983 wet season.

Culture or variety	Days to 50% flowering	Seed-to-seed duration (d)			Panicles (no./hill)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
		Normal	In the experiment	Extended			
Cul. 169	116	142	146	4	9.4	28.0	1.9
Cul. 4	112	140	142	2	10.1	36.7	3.2
Cul. 126	108	138	138	0	8.9	33.6	1.6
Jaya	110	135	140	5	8.3	34.6	2.2
MO. 5	104	120	134	14	11.9	34.0	3.0
MO. 6	104	120	134	14	7.0	29.6	2.0
Jyothi	98	115	128	13	7.3	32.4	2.8
Cul. 1954	92	113	122	9	10.8	25.8	1.8
Karthika	105	110	135	25	9.9	32.9	2.9
Cul. 25331	99	108	129	21	8.2	39.2	1.7
Cul. 25337	104	108	134	26	8.2	35.0	2.4
Swarnaprabha	101	108	131	23	7.3	32.1	2.4
Bhagya	80	100	110	10	6.1	35.0	1.5
Onam	80	95	110	15	7.1	34.8	1.7
Cul. 43-1-4	78	95	108	13	5.9	34.6	1.2
LSD (0.05)	4	—	4	—	2.5	1.4	0.8

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Effect of planting date, seedling age, and planting density on late planted wet season rice

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Delayed rains necessitate transplanting overage seedlings in many rainfed rice-growing areas of India. Other constraints to timely transplanting are delayed delivery of canal water and nonavailability of agricultural labor.

We studied the effect of planting date, seedling age, and planting density in a split-plot design during the 1983 and 1984 wet seasons. Soil was a sandy loam of Mahanadi delta, with pH 6.5, cation exchange capacity 11 meq/ 100 g. The water table fluctuated from 10 cm to 40 cm deep. Rice variety CR1018 (155 d duration) was transplanted at

Table 1. Grain yield of CR1018 as influenced by transplanting date, seedling age, and spacing. Cuttack, India, 1983 wet season.

Planting date	Seedling (d)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha) at given spacing				Mean yield (t/ha)
		15 × 15 cm (44)	20 × 15 cm (33)	20 × 20 cm (25)	25 × 20 cm (20)	
15 Jul	30	5.3	5.8	6.1	5.7	5.7
15 Aug	30	4.4	5.1	4.8	4.4	4.6
15 Aug	60	3.7	4.6	4.4	4.4	4.2
15 Sep	30	2.3	2.6	1.9	2.2	3.0
15 Sep	60	3.5	3.3	2.4	3.1	2.9
Mean		3.8	4.3	3.9	3.9	
LSD (0.05) main plot (planting date × seedling age)				—	0.4	
Subplot (spacing)				—	0.4	
Interaction				—	ns	

^aNumbers in parentheses give the plant population/m².

populations of 20,25, 33, and 44 hills/ m².

Grain yield was reduced 18% with mid-Aug transplanting and 44% with mid-Sep in 1983, and 22% and 44%, respectively, in 1984 (Table 1, 2). Using

30- or 60-d-old seedlings did not affect mid-Aug transplanting yield; 60-d-old seedlings were significantly superior to 30-d-old seedlings with mid-Sep transplanting. Spacing seedlings 20 × 15 cm was optimum. □